

FINITE ELEMENT EVALUATION OF FULL 3D EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF d_{31} PIEZOELECTRIC MACRO-FIBRE COMPOSITES

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Abstract. Piezoelectric Macro-Fibre Composites (MFC) transducers have become very popular since they combine the conformability of epoxy-matrix composites and the electromechanical energy density of piezoceramic materials. Since they are heterogeneous and made of several different materials (piezoceramic fibres, epoxy matrix, electrode and protective layers), a methodology is required to relate their effective properties with the individual properties of its components. This work presents the evaluation of all necessary effective properties for a full 3D finite element analysis. For the evaluation of the remaining effective piezoelectric coefficients, new local problems were added to those presented in the literature. The results are compared to those available in the literature and provided by the manufacturer. A discussion on the full 3D effective properties and their application for full 3D finite element analysis of smart structures with bonded MFCs is also presented.

Keywords: Macro-Fibre Composites, Finite element homogenization, 3D piezoelectric effective properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric Macro-Fibre Composites (MFC) transducers have become very popular since they combine the conformability of epoxy-matrix composites and the electromechanical energy density of piezoceramic materials [1]. Since they are heterogeneous and made of several different materials (piezoceramic fibres, epoxy matrix, electrode and protective layers), a methodology is required to relate their effective properties with the individual properties of its components [2]. Previous studies [3, 4] have shown that the effective properties depend not only on the active layer (piezoceramic fibres and epoxy matrix) but also on electrode and protective layers.

In particular, in [4], the effective elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric properties of a d_{31} MFC, accounting for the effect of electrode and protective layers, were evaluated through finite element (FE) homogenization. An analysis of the effect of the fibre volume fraction, electric boundary conditions (BC) and electric field dependence of soft piezoceramic fibres dielectric and piezoelectric properties on the main effective properties was also presented. Nevertheless, some effective properties, such as the piezoelectric coefficients e_{15} and e_{24} and the dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S , that may be important for completing the full 3D matrices required for FE simulations of the homogenized patches were not presented in [4].

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In the d_{31} operation (transverse response) mode, the dominant electromechanical coupling (in the longitudinal direction) is between the electric field and displacement in x_3 (through-thickness) direction, E_3 and D_3 , and x_1 (fibre longitudinal direction) normal stress and strain, T_1 and S_1 . Thus, the evaluation of the piezoelectric e_{31}/d_{31} , elastic c_{11}^E/s_{11}^E and dielectric $\epsilon_{33}^S/\epsilon_{33}^T$ coefficients is necessary to qualify these composite transducers as sensors and actuators. Nevertheless, due to the anisotropy of the resulting MFC piezoelectric composite effective behavior, it is important to analyze properties related to through-width deformation, which are e_{32} , d_{32} , c_{22}^E , c_{12}^E . Besides, in order to provide complete 3D effective properties matrices for the d_{31} MFC and, hence, be able to use them in 3D FE modeling and simulation, the remaining properties, related to the in-plane electrical excitation, e_{15} , e_{24} , $\epsilon_{11}^S/\epsilon_{11}^T$ and $\epsilon_{22}^S/\epsilon_{22}^T$ need also to be evaluated.

3 EVALUATION OF d_{31} MFC FULL 3D EFFECTIVE ELECTROMECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The evaluation of the effective coefficients that are important to a d_{31} MFC, as discussed in the previous section, is done in this work using the so-called average quantity-based FE homogenization technique proposed in [3]. It is based on the evaluation of the average stresses, strains, electric fields and electric displacements in a FE model of a Representative Volume Element (RVE) of the MFC when subjected to properly chosen mechanical and electrical boundary and periodicity conditions. With these averaged quantities and using the constitutive equations of an equivalent orthotropic piezoelectric material, described in the previous section, the effective elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric coefficients of the MFC are evaluated. It is important to account for symmetric or periodic mechanical and electrical BC in directions x_1 and x_2 , since the RVE is obtained from a through-thickness cut of the real MFC.

The active layer RVE is built with one longitudinal section of the piezoceramic macro-fibre (through-thickness poled and electroded) between two Epoxy inserts. Both upper and lower surfaces of the active layer are covered by a thin electrode layer, composed of two Copper and one Epoxy layers representing a section of the fingered electrode layer. Finally, electrode layers are covered by a homogeneous Kapton protective layer. The RVE boundaries are denoted X_1^- , X_1^+ , X_2^- , X_2^+ , X_3^- and X_3^+ (Figure 2). To obtain a more realistic analysis, electric potential BC are imposed at the electrodes on surfaces Γ_e^- and Γ_e^+ , which represent the areas covered by Copper electrodes and piezoceramic fibre electrodes (at top and bottom surfaces of the piezoceramic fibres).

Average strains and electric fields can be imposed to the RVE using displacements and voltage BC, as

$$u_i^{X_j^+} - u_i^{X_j^-} = \bar{S}_{ij}(x_j^{X_j^+} - x_j^{X_j^-}), \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \quad (2)$$

$$\phi^{X_\alpha^+} - \phi^{X_\alpha^-} = -\bar{E}_\alpha(x_\alpha^{X_\alpha^+} - x_\alpha^{X_\alpha^-}), \quad \alpha = 1, 2, \quad \phi^{\Gamma_e^+} - \phi^{\Gamma_e^-} = -\bar{E}_3(x_3^{\Gamma_e^+} - x_3^{\Gamma_e^-}). \quad (3)$$

The resulting average strains, stresses, electric fields and electric displacements could be defined by the following integrals over the RVE volume

$$\bar{S}_q = \frac{1}{V} \int_V S_q dV, \quad \bar{T}_p = \frac{1}{V} \int_V T_p dV, \quad p, q = 1, \dots, 6, \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{E}_k = \frac{1}{V} \int_V E_k dV, \quad \bar{D}_i = \frac{1}{V} \int_V D_i dV, \quad i, k = 1, 2, 3. \quad (5)$$

Since the RVE is discretized in a number of finite elements, these integrals can only be approximated by a sum over averaged element values multiplied by the respective element volume divided by total volume of the RVE, such that

$$\bar{S}_q = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N S_q^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad \bar{T}_p = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N T_p^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad p, q = 1, \dots, 6, \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{E}_k = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N E_k^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad \bar{D}_i = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^N D_i^{(e)} V^{(e)}}{\sum_{e=1}^N V^{(e)}}, \quad i, k = 1, 2, 3. \quad (7)$$

where $V^{(e)}$ is the element e volume. $S_q^{(e)}$, $T_p^{(e)}$, $E_k^{(e)}$ and $D_i^{(e)}$ are the average strains, stresses, electric fields and electric displacements evaluated at element e . N is the number of finite elements used to discretize the RVE.

The elastic coefficients related to normal strains and stresses c_{pq}^E , $p, q = 1, 2, 3$ were evaluated using three local problems for which a normal strain S_q ($q = 1, 2, 3$) is imposed, through relative normal displacements $u_q^{X_q^+} - u_q^{X_q^-}$. Also, in order to obtain $\bar{S}_j = 0$ for $j \neq q$, the normal displacements u_j for each pair of nodes at opposing surfaces X_j^- and X_j^+ are forced to be equal (symmetrically coupled degrees of freedom). Then, starting from the e -form constitutive equations (1), the effective SC elastic coefficients can be evaluated using

$$c_{pq}^E = \bar{T}_p / \bar{S}_q, \quad p, q = 1, 2, 3, \quad (8)$$

in which the average stresses \bar{T}_p and strains \bar{S}_q are evaluated using (6).

The stress piezoelectric coefficients e_{31} , e_{32} and e_{33} can be also obtained from the local problems used to evaluate c_{1j}^E , c_{2j}^E and c_{3j}^E , respectively, that is where normal stress states in directions x_1 , x_2 and x_3 are approximated. From the e -form constitutive equations (1), e_{31} , e_{32} and e_{33} can be obtained through evaluation of the average electric displacement D_3 such that

$$e_{31} = \bar{D}_3 / \bar{S}_1, \quad e_{32} = \bar{D}_3 / \bar{S}_2, \quad e_{33} = \bar{D}_3 / \bar{S}_3, \quad (9)$$

where the average normal strains \bar{S}_1 , \bar{S}_2 and \bar{S}_3 and electric displacement \bar{D}_3 are evaluated using the FE approximations of (6) and (7).

The evaluation of the SC elastic coefficients related to shear strains and stresses c_{pp}^E , $p = 4, 5, 6$, is performed using other three local problems for which shear strains S_{ik} ($S_{23} = S_4/2$, $S_{13} = S_5/2$ and $S_{12} = S_6/2$) are applied to approximate a pure shear stress state in the planes $x_2 - x_3$, $x_1 - x_3$ and $x_1 - x_2$ by imposing relative shear displacements $u_i^{X_k^+} - u_i^{X_k^-}$ at surfaces X_k^+ / X_k^- and $u_k^{X_i^+} - u_k^{X_i^-}$ at surfaces X_i^+ / X_i^- . In addition, normal displacements at the boundary surfaces parallel to each shear plane of interest are symmetrically coupled to ensure zero strains perpendicular to the shear plane. Then, the evaluation of the effective shear elastic coefficients is performed in terms of the average shear stresses \bar{T}_p and strains \bar{S}_p using

$$c_{pp}^E = \bar{T}_p / \bar{S}_p, \quad p = 4, 5, 6. \quad (10)$$

A SC electric BC is ensured in both previous cases, (8) and (10), setting the voltage degrees of freedom (dof) in the electrodes at surfaces Γ_e^- and Γ_e^+ to zero. Table 1 indicates symmetric BC for the electric potential along directions x_1 and x_2 for the X_1^- / X_1^+ and X_2^- / X_2^+ RVE surfaces.

The stress piezoelectric coefficients e_{24} and e_{15} can be also obtained from the local problems used to evaluate the SC elastic coefficients related to shear strains and stresses c_{pp}^E , $p = 4, 5, 6$. Indeed, from the e -form constitutive equations (1), e_{24} and e_{15} can be obtained through evaluation of the average electric displacement D_2 and D_1 , respectively, such that

$$e_{24} = \bar{D}_2 / \bar{S}_4, \quad (11)$$

$$e_{15} = \bar{D}_1 / \bar{S}_5. \quad (12)$$

For the evaluation of the blocked dielectric coefficient e_{33}^S , another local problem is set up for which an electric voltage $\phi^{\Gamma_e^+} = h_p$ (in value) is applied to the electrode at surface Γ_e^+ while the voltage at the opposite

Table 1: Boundary conditions (displacement/electric potential) and relations used to evaluate the full 3D effective material properties of a d_{31} piezoelectric MFC.

Problem	X_1^-/X_1^+	X_2^-/X_2^+	X_3^-/X_3^+	Γ_e^-/Γ_e^+	Relation
1	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{1j}^E = \bar{T}_j/\bar{S}_1$ (8) $e_{31} = \bar{D}_3/\bar{S}_1$ (9)
2	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{2j}^E = \bar{T}_j/\bar{S}_2$ (8) $e_{32} = \bar{D}_3/\bar{S}_2$ (9)
3	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = q$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{3j}^E = \bar{T}_j/\bar{S}_3$ (8) $e_{33} = \bar{D}_3/\bar{S}_3$ (9)
4	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = q$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{44}^E = \bar{T}_4/\bar{S}_4$ (10) $e_{24} = \bar{D}_2/\bar{S}_4$ (11)
5	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = q$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{55}^E = \bar{T}_5/\bar{S}_5$ (10) $e_{15} = \bar{D}_1/\bar{S}_5$ (12)
6	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = q$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = 0; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$c_{66}^E = \bar{T}_6/\bar{S}_6$ (10)
7	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ -	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$\epsilon_{33}^S = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3$ (13)
8	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$\epsilon_{33}^T = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3$ (14)
9	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_1^{i+} - u_1^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{11}^S = \bar{D}_1/\bar{E}_1$ (15)
10	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{11}^T = \bar{D}_1/\bar{E}_1$ (17)
11	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_3^{i+} - u_3^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	$u_2^{i+} - u_2^{i-} = 0$ $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{22}^S = \bar{D}_2/\bar{E}_2$ (16)
12	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} = q; \phi^{i-} = 0$	- $\phi^{i+} - \phi^{i-} = 0$	- -	$\epsilon_{22}^T = \bar{D}_2/\bar{E}_2$ (18)

electrode (at surface Γ_e^-) is set to zero so that a unitary electric field in the x_3 direction is generated. The blocked condition is approximated by preventing the normal strains S_1 , S_2 and S_3 through the imposition of equal normal displacements u_j ($j = 1, 2, 3$) for each pair of nodes at opposing surfaces X_j^- and X_j^+ . The dielectric coefficient is then obtained from

$$\epsilon_{33}^S = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3. \quad (13)$$

It could also be interesting to evaluate the free dielectric coefficient ϵ_{33}^T . For that, a local problem is designed in which an electric voltage $\phi^{\Gamma_e^+} = h_p$ (in value) is applied to the electrode at surface Γ_e^+ while the voltage at the opposite electrode (at surface Γ_e^-) is set to zero so that a unitary electric field in the x_3 direction is generated. To approximate the free condition, no mechanical displacements BC are imposed to the RVE. The dielectric coefficient is then obtained from

$$\epsilon_{33}^T = \bar{D}_3/\bar{E}_3. \quad (14)$$

For the evaluation of the blocked dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S , two other local problems are set up for the imposition of in-plane electric fields in x_1 and x_2 directions, respectively. Since there are no physical electrodes in the corresponding planes x_2/x_3 and x_1/x_3 , the electric potentials are applied to the boundaries of the RVE, namely X_1^- and X_1^+ for the application of an electric field in x_1 direction and X_2^- and X_2^+ for the application of an electric field in x_2 direction. Additionally, it is assumed that the actual Copper electrode is electrically inactive but is kept in place to maintain the RVE stiffness behavior unchanged. Since the application of an electric field perpendicular to the piezoelectric fiber poling direction is expected to generate a transverse

shear strain, the blocked condition is approximated by preventing the shear strains S_4 , for the evaluation of ϵ_{22}^S with application of an electric field E_2 , or S_5 , for the evaluation of ϵ_{11}^S with application of an electric field E_1 . The dielectric coefficients are then obtained from

$$\epsilon_{11}^S = \bar{D}_1 / \bar{E}_1, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{S}_5 = 0, \quad (15)$$

and

$$\epsilon_{22}^S = \bar{D}_2 / \bar{E}_2, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{S}_4 = 0. \quad (16)$$

The free dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^T and ϵ_{22}^T may also be evaluated with similar local problems but without mechanical displacements BC imposed to the RVE, to approximate a free condition,

$$\epsilon_{11}^T = \bar{D}_1 / \bar{E}_1, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{T}_5 = 0, \quad (17)$$

and

$$\epsilon_{22}^T = \bar{D}_2 / \bar{E}_2, \quad \text{with BC aiming at } \bar{T}_4 = 0. \quad (18)$$

The local problems used to evaluate the full 3D material effective electromechanical properties of the piezoelectric d_{31} MFC RVE are summarized in Table 1, where u_j^{i-} and u_j^{i+} are the displacements in direction j and ϕ^{i-} and ϕ^{i+} are the electric potentials at i -th node of opposite surfaces; q is an arbitrary non-null value.

The MFC effective material static electromechanical coupling coefficients (EMCC) k_{3j}^2 may be evaluated as

$$k_{3j}^2 = \frac{d_{3j}^2}{s_{jj}^E \epsilon_{33}^T}. \quad (19)$$

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND VALIDATION

A FE model was built in Ansys[®] to solve the local problems and evaluate the full 3D effective electromechanical properties of a 5-layered piezoelectric d_{31} MFC RVE, using a fiber volume fraction (FVF) of 0.86 for the PZT+Epoxy Active Layer. The 3D 20-Node coupled-field solid FE SOLID226 was used to mesh all volumes. It has the three displacement translations along the Cartesian coordinate system axes and the electric potential as nodal dof. A mesh of 9900 finite elements was used considering 25 divisions in x_1 direction (17 divisions for the Epoxy layer and 4 divisions for each electrode layer), 18 divisions in x_2 direction (14 divisions for the PZT fibre and 2 divisions for each Epoxy layer) and 22 divisions in x_3 direction (12 divisions for the PZT layer, 2 divisions for each electrode layer and 3 divisions for each protective layer). The dimensions considered for this RVE are $h_P = 180 \mu\text{m}$, $h_K = 40 \mu\text{m}$, and $h_C = 18 \mu\text{m}$, $L_E = 420 \mu\text{m}$, $L_C = 80 \mu\text{m}$, $w_E = 28.35 \mu\text{m}$ and $w_P = 348.3 \mu\text{m}$ [2]. The material properties for the piezoceramic material Sonox P502, taken from [2], are: $s_{11}^E = s_{22}^E = 18.5 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{33}^E = 20.7 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{12}^E = -6.29 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{13}^E = -6.23 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{44}^E = s_{55}^E = 33.2 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $s_{66}^E = 52.3 \text{ pm}^2/\text{N}$, $d_{31} = d_{32} = -185 \text{ pC}/\text{N}$, $d_{33} = 440 \text{ pC}/\text{N}$, $d_{15} = d_{24} = 560 \text{ pC}/\text{N}$, $\epsilon_{11}^T = \epsilon_{22}^T = 1950\epsilon_0$, $\epsilon_{33}^T = 1850\epsilon_0$. The material properties for the other constituents, taken from [5], are: Epoxy – $Y = 2.5 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.42$ and $\epsilon = 4.25\epsilon_0$; Kapton – $Y = 2.5 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.34$ and $\epsilon = 3.4\epsilon_0$; and Copper electrode – $Y = 110 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.34$ and $\epsilon = 5\epsilon_0$, with $\epsilon_0 = 8.854 \text{ pF}/\text{m}$.

A discussion on the local problems #1, #2, #3, #6, #7 and #8 was presented in [4]. Since similar results were obtained for these local problems, here, it is chosen to focus on the new local problems from now on.

Local problems #4 and #5, that are mainly intended to evaluate the effective shear modulus c_{44}^E and c_{55}^E , respectively, were also used to evaluate the effective stress piezoelectric coefficients e_{24} and e_{15} . Although

these coefficients are usually less important in terms of operation performance of d_{31} MFCs, they are required to complete the full 3D piezoelectric matrix necessary for 3D FE simulations. The approximation is mainly based on the evaluation of the average electric displacement in the in-plane x_2 and x_1 directions according to (11) and (12), respectively. Thus, the distributions of electric displacement and field and shear strain and stress are shown in Figures 3, for local problem #4, and 4, for local problem #5.

Figure 3: Electric displacement D_2 (a) and field E_2 (b) and shear strain S_4 (c) and stress T_4 (d) induced by shear displacements applied to the d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #4).

Figure 4: Electric displacement D_1 (a) and field E_1 (b) and shear strain S_5 (c) and stress T_5 (d) induced by shear displacements applied to the d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #5).

Although most of the shear strains are localized in the protective layers, in both cases, it is noticeable that non-negligible electric displacements are developed in the piezoelectric fiber. Hence, despite being smaller than the e_{3j} effective coefficients, both e_{24} and e_{15} are in the same order of magnitude, meaning that actuation/sensing using the d_{24} and d_{15} modes could be possible if actual electrodes were installed in the X_2^-/X_2^+ or X_1^-/X_1^+ faces. As generally this is not the case, these effective coefficients shall be used only to complete the full 3D piezoelectric matrix for FE simulations.

In addition, other effective coefficients required to fill the full 3D e -form properties matrix are the effective blocked dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S . For their evaluation, additional local problems are required since it is necessary to apply an electric field along the in-plane x_1 and x_2 directions. Thus, although there are no actual electrodes in the X_1^-/X_1^+ and X_2^-/X_2^+ faces, electric potentials were applied to these faces to generate the required electric fields. Since the application of such electric fields induces shear strains in the RVE, these strains are blocked through displacements BC. Then, the effective blocked dielectric coefficients ϵ_{11}^S and ϵ_{22}^S are evaluated in local problems #9 and #11 using the approximations to the average electric displacements and fields according to (15) and (16), respectively. The distributions of interest in these cases are the electric displacement and field and the shear strain and stress. These are shown in Figures 5, for the evaluation of ϵ_{11}^S , and 6, for the evaluation of ϵ_{22}^S . Figure 5 shows that the application of an electric field in the x_1 direction (local problem #9) induces important transverse shear strains S_5 in the piezoelectric fiber that are counterbalanced by shear strains in the protective layers so that the RVE is not sheared in its boundaries. The resulting effect

is that the effective dielectric coefficient ϵ_{11}^S is of the same order of magnitude as the through-thickness one ϵ_{33}^S as shown in Table 2. On the other hand, for the application of an electric field in the x_2 direction (local problem #11), although the global behavior of the shear strains that are induced both in the piezoelectric fiber and, in opposite sense, in the protective layer, the effect is much less important. This is due to the fact that the electric potentials are applied to the X_2^-/X_2^+ faces that are constituted by non-piezoelectric material (Epoxy, for the active layer, and Epoxy, Copper and Kapton, for the covering outer layers). This leads to an important reduction of the electric potential induced in the piezoelectric fiber faces. For this reason, the effective dielectric coefficient ϵ_{22}^S is much smaller than the other two, as shown in Table 2.

Figure 5: Electric displacement D_1 (a) and field E_1 (b) and shear strain S_5 (c) and stress T_5 (d) induced by electric potentials difference applied to the blocked d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #9).

Figure 6: Electric displacement D_2 (a) and field E_2 (b) and shear strain S_4 (c) and stress T_4 (d) induced by electric potentials difference applied to the blocked d_{31} MFC RVE (local problem #11).

In order to validate the FE homogenization, the evaluated full 3D effective coefficients of the d_{31} MFC were compared to previous analytical and experimental results available in the literature. The results obtained here for the full 5-layered MFC were compared to data provided by the manufacturer of a commercial d_{31} MFC (Smart Material Corp.) [6], with the same nominal geometrical and material properties for its constituents considered in the present work. Results are summarized in Table 2. Notice that not all coefficients are provided by the manufacturer. Nevertheless, it can be concluded that the here 3D FE-evaluated effective electromechanical properties represent very well the actual (manufactured) d_{31} MFC. The only coefficient presenting a significant relative deviation (24%) to the data from manufacturer is the transversal elastic modulus Y_2^E , but this may be explained by the fact that the actual width of the Copper electrode finger (L_C) is not known and was only visually approximated from a microphotography presented by the original prototype developer at NASA Langley Research Center [1]. A wider Copper electrode finger would lead to a higher transversal elastic modulus Y_2^E . It could also affect the transverse piezoelectric coefficients e_{32} and d_{32} . The results obtained for the most important effective coefficients, Y_1^E , d_{31} and ϵ_{11}^T , are all below 4% of relative deviation (3.4%, 1.3% and 0.9% respectively) compared to the data provided by the Smart Material Corp. [6]. The present results were also compared to those shown in [4]. Both results were almost the same despite the fact that, in the present analysis,

the FE mesh is substantially finer than that considered in [4].

Table 2: Effective material properties of d_{31} MFC (*: values obtained post-processing data provided in the reference).

Coefficient	FE [4]	Present FE	Manufacturer [6]	Coefficient	FE [4]	Present FE	Manufacturer [6]
Y_1^E (GPa)	31.40	31.37	30.34	d_{31} (pC/N)	-172.2	-172.3	-170
Y_2^E (GPa)	19.80	19.69	15.86	d_{32} (pC/N)	-133.8	-133.2	–
Y_3^E (GPa)	9.03	9.02	–	d_{33} (pC/N)	310.0	308.9	–
G_{23}^E (GPa)	2.17	2.16	–	d_{15} (pC/N)	–	334.9	–
G_{13}^E (GPa)	2.42	2.42	–	d_{24} (pC/N)	–	219.3	–
G_{12}^E (GPa)	5.34	5.33	5.52	e_{31} (C/m ²)	-6.04	-6.03	–
ν_{12}^E	0.36	0.36	0.31	e_{32} (C/m ²)	-3.47	-3.44	–
ν_{23}^E	0.37	0.37	–	e_{33} (C/m ²)	1.48	1.48	–
ν_{13}^E	0.42	0.42	–	e_{15} (C/m ²)	–	0.81	–
$\epsilon_{11}^T/\epsilon_0$	–	1019.3	–	e_{24} (C/m ²)	–	0.47	–
$\epsilon_{22}^T/\epsilon_0$	–	24.1	–	k_{31}^2 (%)	6.7	6.7	6.4*
$\epsilon_{33}^T/\epsilon_0$	1572.1	1573.3	1558.6	k_{31}	0.26	0.26	0.25*
$\epsilon_{11}^S/\epsilon_0$	–	988.6	–				
$\epsilon_{22}^S/\epsilon_0$	–	24.1	–				
$\epsilon_{33}^S/\epsilon_0$	1179.7	1181.7	–				

5 APPLICATION OF EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES FOR THE ANALYSIS OF A BONDED d_{31} MFC

To exemplify the utility of the full 3D effective properties, the obtained values were applied for a FE analysis of a smart structure composed of a d_{31} MFC bonded to a metallic plate, using an Epoxy adhesive, with a tip mass (Figure 7). The benchmark was taken from [7] where the application of MFC transducers for energy harvesting was studied. The experimental results presented therein were also considered for verification of the present FE model and results. The results presented in [7] indicate a substantial non-linearity of the structure. The fundamental resonance frequency ranges between 30 and 31 Hz, depending on the imposed base acceleration. The voltage output (in RMS) of a resistive circuit connected to the MFC ranges between 6.5 and 10 Vs²/m.

Figure 7: Cantilever plate with adhesively bonded d_{31} MFC patch and tip mass.

A FE model was implemented in Ansys[®] following the geometrical and material properties provided in [7] and using the full 3D effective properties for the d_{31} MFC obtained in the present work. The plate is made of Aluminum with length 70 mm, width 10.6 mm, thickness 0.67 mm, Young's modulus 68.9 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.33 and mass density 2700 kg m⁻³. The adhesive layer is made of Epoxy 3M DP-460 with length 28 mm, width 7 mm, thickness 0.1 mm, Young's modulus 2.7 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.4 and mass density 1100 kg m⁻³.

The MFC patch is from Smart Material Co., model 2807-P2, with length and width equal to those of the adhesive layer and thickness 0.3 mm. The tip mass is composed of two Acrylic blocks with length 15 mm, width 25 mm and thickness 5 mm, which are fixed using two screws. The total mass, including the screws, is 7.3 g. To avoid modeling the screws, the total mass was uniformly distributed in the two Acrylic blocks. Non-uniform rectangular meshes of $87 \times 16 \times 2$, $38 \times 10 \times 2$, $38 \times 10 \times 2$, and $6 \times 22 \times 2$ 20-node solid finite elements were considered for the host plate, adhesive layer, MFC, and each tip mass block, respectively. A modal analysis was performed for SC and open-circuit (OC) electric BC on the MFC effective top and bottom surface electrodes. The first five natural frequencies and the corresponding effective (structural) modal EMCC, defined as $EMCC = 1 - f_{SC}^2 / f_{OC}^2$, are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: First five natural frequencies in SC and OC electric BC, and corresponding effective modal EMCC, for the plate with bonded MFC patch and tip mass.

Mode	1	2	3	4	5
f_{SC} (Hz)	29.9	171.1	364.9	372.5	1098.2
f_{OC} (Hz)	30.3	171.1	364.9	374.0	1098.9
EMCC (%)	2.18	0	0	0.79	0.12

The frequency response function (FRF) of the voltage output for an imposed base acceleration was also simulated in Ansys[®]. For that, a global damping factor of 4% was estimated from the FRF presented in [7] and used as input in Ansys[®]. The obtained peak output is 11.2 Vs²/m, a little higher than the experimental one.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the evaluation of all necessary effective properties of a d_{31} piezoelectric macro-fibre composite for a full 3D FE analysis. Compared to the existing methodology and results [4], for the evaluation of the remaining effective piezoelectric and dielectric coefficients, new local problems were added. The results are compared to those available in [4] and provided by the manufacturer [6]. An application of the effective properties for full 3D FE analysis of a cantilever Aluminum plate with a bonded MFC patch was also presented indicating good correspondence between numerical and experimental results [7].

REFERENCES

- [1] W.K. Wilkie, G.R. Bryant and J.W. High, Low-cost piezocomposite actuator for structural control applications, in *Proceedings of the SPIE Int. Symp. on Smart Struct. and Mater.*, March 5-9, 2000.
- [2] A. Deraemaeker, H. Nasser, A. Benjeddou and A. Preumont, Mixing rules for the piezoelectric properties of macro fiber composites, *J. Intel. Mater. Syst. Struct.*, Vol. 20, pp. 1475–1482, 2009.
- [3] M.A. Trindade and A. Benjeddou. Finite element homogenization technique for the characterization of d_{15} shear piezoelectric macro-fibre composites, *Smart Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 20, No. 7, p. 075012, 2011.
- [4] M.A. Trindade and A. Benjeddou, Finite element characterisation of multilayer d_{31} piezoelectric macro-fibre composites, *Compos. Struct.*, Vol. 151, pp. 47–57, 2016.
- [5] B. Kranz, A. Benjeddou and W.-G. Drossel, Numerical and experimental characterizations of longitudinally polarized piezoelectric d_{15} shear macro-fiber composites, *Acta Mech.*, Vol. 224, No. 11, pp. 2471–2487, 2013.
- [6] Smart Material Corp., Macro-fibre composites technical data, www.smart-material.com, Sarasota (2009).
- [7] D. Upadrashta and Y. Yang, Experimental investigation of performance reliability of macro fiber composite for piezoelectric energy harvesting applications, *Sensor Actuat. A: Phys.*, Vol. 244, pp. 223–232, 2016.

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVE ELECTROMECHANICAL COUPLING OF A VIBRATING AIRCRAFT-TYPE HYBRID HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANEL WITH BONDED PIEZOELECTRIC d_{31} MACRO-FIBRE COMPOSITE (MFC) PATCH

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Abstract. This work presents the *experimental evaluation* challenges of the modal effective *Electro-Mechanical Coupling Coefficient* (EMCC) of a *hybrid sandwich plate*, made of regular (hexagonal) Aluminium *honeycomb core* and woven glass fibre-reinforced polymer *composite faces*, on which is bonded a piezoelectric transverse response (d_{31}) *Macro-Fibre Composite* (MFC) large patch. The testing challenges come from the very *light weight* of the hybrid sandwich panel and the resulting difficulties to consider, without damaging it, different mechanical boundary conditions (BCs) along its lateral edges. This experimental campaign, using an *impedance analyser*, complements an earlier one that used an LCR meter. The latter provided only the EMCC of the first three electro-mechanically coupled modes under free-free (F-F) BCs, while the former reached *more accurately* eight ones for F-F and *clamped-free* (cantilever) BCs. Beside graphical form, the obtained frequency and effective EMCC results are given in tabular form, so that they can be used as reference for validating/correlating future numerical models.

Keywords: Experiment; EMCC; Vibration; Hybrid honeycomb sandwich; Piezoelectric; MFC.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hybrid honeycomb sandwiches, made of different materials for the core and faces, find popular usage as trim panels in modern aircraft structures for alleviating their weight, noise or vibration. Hybridization can be reached by combining Aluminium (Al) [1-3], paper [1, 4, 5] and Carbon (CFRP) [2, 4, 5] or Glass (GFRP) [3, 6, 7] Fibre-Reinforced Polymer woven *composite materials*. Hybrid honeycomb sandwiches are often functionalized through bonding *piezoelectric* (PE) ceramic [1, 2] or *Macro-Fibre Composite* (MFC) [4-7] patches that are used as sensors and actuators for wave propagation [1, 2], structural health monitoring [5] and active vibration control [4]. Besides, for vibration-based transduction applications, like PE shunted damping (PSD) and energy harvesting (PEH), the so-called modal effective *Electro-Mechanical Coupling Coefficient* (EMCC) is a key performance indicator [8] that can be maximized by adequately selecting the host-patch materials couple and optimally positioning the patch on the host laminated CFRP composite or hybrid (GFRP skins, Al core) honeycomb sandwich structures [6]. However, except the earlier works [6, 7], no others have been found in the open literature on the experimental evaluation of the modal effective EMCC of hybrid honeycomb sandwiches bonded with MFC patches. Therefore, this work presents for the first time *Experimental Impedance Analyser (EIA)*-based evaluation challenges of the modal effective EMCC of a *hybrid sandwich plate*, made of regular (hexagonal) *Al honeycomb core* and woven *GFRP composite faces*, on which is bonded a PE *transverse mode* (d_{31}) MFC large patch. The testing challenges come from the very *light weight* of the panel and the resulting difficulties to consider, without damaging it, *different mechanical Boundary Conditions* (BCs), like free-free (F-F) and clamped-free (C-F) lateral edges of the hybrid sandwich [3]. This new campaign complements an LCR (Inductance-L, Capacitance-C, Resistance-R) meter-based earlier one [6, 7], that provided only the EMCC of the first three *electromechanically coupled modes* (EMC), by reaching *more accurately* eight ones under F-F and C-F (*cantilever*) BCs.

In the following, first, the next section describes the experimental setup, materials and devices. Then, the third section presents the resulting experimental modal analyses (EMA) of the EIA measurements and their use for the *Short-Circuit* (SC) and *Open-Circuit* (OC) frequencies extractions and modal effective EMCC post-treatments. Next, the EIA measurements and results are compared to those of experimental LCR meter analyses for the respectively considered F-F or/and C-F BCs. The latter are popular in PSD and PEH, while the former are useful for inverse identification. Finally, conclusions and perspectives are given as a closure.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP: MATERIALS AND DEVICES

This section describes the EMA setup, its measurement devices and the aircraft-type hybrid honeycomb sandwich and surface-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch materials used for the experimental evaluation of the modal effective EMCC of such vibrating smart structure under F-F (Figure 1a) and C-F (Figure 1b) BCs at its lateral edges. For this, the *impedance analyzer* WK 6500B from Wayne Kerr (WK), shown in Figure 1, is used to graphically display the *module* and *phase* of the *voltage-to-current ratio* of the *capacitance* of the d_{31} MFC patch, that is surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under the considered two BCs. The *excitation voltage* was fixed to 1V, while the *impedance analyzer resolution* was set to 1600 points for a considered frequency range.

Figure 1: EIA setup for modal effective EMCC evaluation under (a) F-F and (b) C-F BCs.

As shown in Figure 1a and zoomed-in in Figure 2a, the F-F BCs were realized by posing the tested smart structure on two foam pieces, while the C-F BCs were realized by accurately (with good quality alignment) fastening one lateral edge along 1 cm, as shown in Figure 1b and zoomed-in in Figure 2b. It is worthy to mention that the influence of the smart coupon position on the foams was found negligible, as considering two different positions led to the same *resonant* (SC) and *anti-resonant* (OC) frequencies of their related MFC *capacitances*.

Figure 2: Zoom-in of Figure 1 on realized (a) F-F BCs and (b) C-F BCs' clamp.

The optimal positioning of the MFC patch on the vibrating hybrid sandwich honeycomb is modal shape and BCs-dependent [9]. Hence, a numerical modal analysis (NMA) of the bare honeycomb sandwich coupon was conducted, using a developed *detailed* finite element (FE) approach [3], in order to locate the maxima of the *modal strain energy* (MSE) where to bond the MFC patch. The resulting optimized configuration is that in Figure 2a, where the MFC patch is located 3 cm from one lateral edge (see also Figure 1b) and *centered* along the host *width*. This *optimal* position *maximizes* the effective EMCC of the *first mode*, the target of the PSD and PEH applications.

The PE d_{31} MFC patch (M-8528-P2), from Smart Materials GmbH (Germany), has global in-plane dimensions of $103 \times 31 \text{ mm}^2$ and useful *active area* ones of $85 \times 28 \text{ mm}^2$ while its *thickness* is 0.3 mm. In order to connect it to the impedance analyzer (Figure 1), very thin wires were soldered to its net-like electrodes' dedicated soldering pads (see Figure 2a). The MFC patch was *glued* with *Cyanolit* (super glue) to one of the GFRP skins of the hybrid honeycomb sandwich, which has length x width x thickness of $183 \times 52 \times 4.6 \text{ mm}^3$. More details on the latter host structure geometrical and material properties can be found in [3]. The combined hybrid honeycomb sandwich and MFC patch have a measured mass of 13.75 g, indicating a *very light* smart structure. Considering the protecting polyamide film, electrodes, soldering pads and glue allowed to *update* the d_{31} MFC patch volume mass density to 6300 Kg/m^3 (*active area*-based value is 5440 Kg/m^3 [10]).

3 EXPERIMENTAL IMPEDANCE ANALYSES: FREQUENCIES & EFFECTIVE EMCC

This section first presents the graphical displays of the *absolute* and *phase* of the *voltage-to-current ratio* of the *capacitance* of the d_{31} MFC patch that is surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under the considered two BCs (F-F and C-F). Then, the extracted SC and OC frequencies, approximating respectively the *resonant* (r) and *anti-resonant* (a) ones, are tabulated with the post-treated *experimental* (e) EMCC (K_e^2) from [11]:

$$K_e^2 (\%) = 100 \frac{f_a^2 - f_r^2}{f_a^2} \quad (1)$$

A slightly different, called *numerical* (n), EMCC expression is traditionally used in PSD applications:

$$K_n^2 (\%) = 100 \frac{f_{oc}^2 - f_{sc}^2}{f_{sc}^2} \quad (2)$$

However, above EMCC expressions were shown [11] to be related by this one:

$$K_e^2 \approx \frac{K_n^2}{K_n^2 + 1} \quad (3)$$

Nevertheless, when $K_n^2 \ll 1$, $K_e^2 \approx K_n^2$ and either of the expressions can be used for evaluating the EMCC.

3.1 Free-free configuration

The module and phase of the capacitance of the F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch are shown in Figure 3, first, for a large (300 Hz-11 kHz) frequency range, in order to evaluate the number of modes present in this range. Then, zooms illustrate missing modes (Figure 4a) or for accurate identification (Figure 4b).

Figure 3: Capacitance module and phase spectra of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Figure 4: Capacitance module and phase spectra of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

As in Figure 5, the phase peak corresponds to the inflexion point between resonance and anti-resonance peaks.

Figure 5: Capacitance combined module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Next, a zoom-in on each mode is displayed in order to identify its resonant (SC) and anti-resonant (OC) frequencies that correspond, respectively, to the maximum and minimum of the capacitance module or the points of inflexion of the ascending and descending branches of the phase, as illustrated in Figure 6 for the first mode.

Figure 6: Identification of mode 1 (a) resonant (SC) and anti-resonant (OC) frequencies from module and phase.

The earlier procedure is applied for identifying the *eight modes*, numbered in Figure 3 and Figure 4, leading to the frequencies and effective EMCC summarized in Table 1. The latter confirms that the *highest* effective EMCC is obtained for the *first mode*, target of PSD and PEH applications. Besides, following (1) and (2) and as $f_{a,OC} > f_{r,SC}$, $K_n^2 > K_e^2$; hence, the numerical EMCC *overestimates* the experimental one. Nevertheless, the differences between them reduces as the former is approaching unity. Besides, it is worthy to recall that the impedance analyzer provides only the characteristics of the EMC modes. Hence, as the *in-plane* (x-y) *bending* and *torsion* modes are known to be electro-mechanically *uncoupled* [9, 11], the modes in Table 1 are the *transverse* (x-z) *bending* modes only. This recall is to be taken into account when using these experimental tabulated results as a reference for validating/correlating numerical (FE for example) ones. Specifically, the order of modes shown in the first column of Table 1 should be made consistent with that resulting from the numerical analysis. That is, the consistent modes order is correctly obtained only after modal shapes (deformation) visualizations.

Table 1: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_r, f_{SC}	f_a, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	600.00	618.07	5.76	6.11
2	1502.92	1523.39	2.67	2.74
3	2751.82	2788.52	2.61	2.69
4	4184.76	4242.32	2.70	2.77
5	6981.76	7089.31	3.01	3.10
6	7722.69	7850.82	3.24	3.35
7	7988.71	8061.02	1.79	1.82
8	8170.71	8319.28	3.54	3.67

3.2 Clamped-free configuration

Under the *same measurement conditions* as the F-F configuration, the module and phase of the capacitance of the C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC patch are shown in Figure 7, first, for the a wide (global) frequency range (100 Hz-8 kHz) in order to evaluate the number of modes present in this range. It can be seen that the latter shows *six modes* that have much lower frequencies than those in Figure 3, due to the clamp presence.

Figure 7: Capacitance module and phase spectra of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Then, the same zoom-in procedure is applied for accurately identifying the *six modes*, numbered in Figure 7, leading to the frequencies and effective EMCC shown in Table 2 from which similar remarks as from Table 1 can be retained, except that the *highest* EMCC (lower value) is here obtained for the *fourth mode* despite its low peak.

Table 2: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_i, f_{SC}	f_a, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	107.25	108.76	2.84	2.76
2	515.46	523.06	2.97	2.88
3	1368.38	1381.45	1.92	1.88
4	2713.41	2769.09	4.15	3.98
5	3194.49	3255.56	3.86	3.72
6	3582.33	3646.46	3.61	3.49

4 COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL LCR METER ANALYSES

This section aims to compare the *LCM Meter*-based measured (*mode-by-mode* and *frequency-by-frequency*) *impedance* (module and phase) figures, tabulated extracted frequencies and post-treated effective EMCC of the PE d_{31} MFC patch, surface-bonded on the hybrid honeycomb sandwich under F-F BCs that were *realized differently*, as this first experimental campaign was conducted few years earlier than the present one. Indeed, the F-F BCs were here realized by *wire suspension* of the smart hybrid honeycomb sandwich, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: *Wire suspension*-realized F-F BCs of the smart hybrid honeycomb sandwich.

The impedance module and phase, measured by an LCR meter, are shown graphically in Figure 9 for the first EMC mode and Figure 10 for the second one. From the latter, notice the poor accuracy around the curves' peaks, due to the LCM meter low frequency resolution (large steps), that shall affect the accuracy of the extraction of the impedance *minimum* (*anti-resonant*, SC) and *maximum* (*resonant*, OC) frequencies (oppositely to the capacitance characteristics) and the EMCC post-treated from them. The corresponding results are shown in Table 3.

Figure 9: EMC mode 1 impedance module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Figure 10: EMC mode 2 impedance module and phase of F-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded PE d_{31} MFC.

Table 3: Frequencies (Hz) and effective EMCC (%) of C-F hybrid honeycomb sandwich-bonded d_{31} MFC.

Mode	f_a, f_{SC}	f_r, f_{OC}	K_e^2	K_n^2
1	590.55	600	3.13	3.23
2	1495	1525	3.90	4.05

Despite the inaccuracy of extractions, the $a_{,SC}$ and $r_{,OC}$ frequencies given in Table 3 show small *relative deviations* (with those in Table 1 that are taken as *reference*, due to their extractions accuracy), particularly for EMC mode 2, of, respectively, -1.57% and -2.92% for EMC mode 1, and -0.53% and 0.11% for EMC mode 2. However, the relative deviations of the EMCC are much higher ($\sim \pm 47\%$, with ‘-’ for mode 1 and ‘+’ for mode 2) as they are proportional to the *frequency measurement resolution* and the *inverse of EMCC values* [12].

5 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Impedance analyser-based experimental evaluations of the modal effective EMCC of a vibrating *hybrid Al honeycomb-woven GFRP composite faces sandwich plate*, bonded with a PE d_{31} MFC large patch, were presented in figures and tables for F-F and C-F lateral edges of the smart panel. The extracted frequencies and post-treated effective EMCC were compared to those from earlier LCR meter-based experimental evaluations [6, 7]. The latter provided only the EMCC of the first two EMC modes under F-F BCs, while the former reached *more accurately eight modes* for F-F and C-F BCs. The present experimental campaign confirmed that the *highest* effective EMCC is that of the *fundamental mode*, the target of PSD and PEH applications, while the earlier experimental campaign showed *lower* graphical and peak (resonant/anti-resonant) frequency extraction *accuracy*, due to the low frequency resolution of the LCR meter. Nevertheless, the provided *tabulated results* of both experimental campaigns can be of valuable use as *reference* for validating/correlating future numerical models. In particular, the use of the detailed FE approach [3] gives a good perspective of the present work, as this will allow the *experimental validation* of the recently *FE-homogenized* 3D electromechanical properties of the here described PE d_{31} MFC [13].

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Song, G. L. Huang and K. Hudson. Guided wave propagation in honeycomb sandwich structures using a piezoelectric actuator/sensor system. *Smart Mater. Struct.* Vol. 18, 125007, 2009.
- [2] D. G. Luchinsky, V. Hafiychuk, V. N. Smelyanskiy, S. Kessler, J. Walker, J. Miller and M. Watson. Modeling wave propagation and scattering from impact damage for structural health monitoring of composite

- sandwich plates. *Struct. Health Monit.* Vol. 12, pp. 296–308, 2013.
- [3] A. Benjeddou and M. Guerich. Free vibration of actual aircraft and spacecraft hexagonal honeycomb sandwich panels: a detailed practical FE approach. *Adv. Aircraft Spacecraft Struct.* Vol. 6, pp. 169-187, 2019.
- [4] A. Zippo, G. Ferrari, M. Amabili, M. Barbieri and F. Pellicano. Active vibration control of a composite sandwich plate. *Compos. Struct.* Vol. 128, pp. 100–114, 2015.
- [5] M. Rebillat, M. Guskov, E. Balmès and N. Mechbal. Simultaneous influence of static load and temperature on the electromechanical signature of piezoelectric elements bonded to composite aeronautic structures. *J. Vib. Acoust.* Vol. 138, 064504, 2016.
- [6] A. Benjeddou. Piezoelectric effective coupling for dynamic control of composites. In *1st Int. Conf. on Composites Dynamics (DYNACOMP)*, Arcachon, 22-24 May 2012.
- [7] A. Benjeddou. Vibration of a honeycomb sandwich structures with an on face bonded macro fibre composite. In *1st Int. Conf. on Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures (ICMAMS)*, Turin, 17-20 June 2018.
- [8] M.A. Trindade and A. Benjeddou. Effective electromechanical coupling coefficients of piezoelectric adaptive structures: critical evaluation and optimization, *Mech. Adv. Mater. Struct.* Vol. 16, pp. 210-223, 2009.
- [9] M. Hamdi, S. Ghanmi, A. Benjeddou and R. Nasri. Robust electromechanical finite element updating for piezoelectric structures effective coupling prediction. *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* Vol 25, pp. 137-154, 2014.
- [10] Smart Materials GmbH, <https://www.smart-material.com/MFC-product-propertiesV2.html>. Oct. 28, 2024.
- [11] A. Benjeddou. Modal effective electromechanical coupling approximate evaluations and simplified analyses: numerical and experimental assessments. *Acta Mech.* Vol. 225, pp. 2721–2742, 2014.
- [12] G. Chevallier and A. Benjeddou. Couplages électromécaniques effectifs dans les structures composites piézoélectriques : caractérisation expérimentales et simulations par éléments finis. *Rev. Compos. Mater. Av.* Vol. 19, pp. 239-264, 2009.
- [13] M. A. Trindade and A. Benjeddou. Finite element evaluation of full 3D effective properties of d_{31} piezoelectric macro-fibre composites. In *8th Int. Conf. on Smart Materials and Nanotechnology in Engineering (SMN)*, Sharjah, 25-28 November, 2024.